

Formation Constants of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Oxovanadium(IV) with Salicylic Acid/5-Sulphosalicylic Acid/8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid and Hippuric Acid

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Equilibrium studies are described on the interaction of oxovanadium(IV) with salicylic acid (SA)/5-sulphosalicylic acid (SSA)/8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (HQSA) in presence of hippuric acid. The formation of 1:1:1 mixed ligand complexes and their hydroxo derivatives inferred from the pH-metric titration curves and formation constants of 1:1:1 ternary complexes have been evaluated at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$). The order of stability of ternary complexes has been found to be the same as that of 1:1 binary complexes involving hydroxy acids.

FROM the view point of the role of metal complexes in biological systems and in analytical separations, the information about the concentration of different species of a metal complex in equilibrium mixtures is of considerable importance and can be predicted on the basis of their formation constants. So in continuation of our earlier work¹⁻⁵ on binary and ternary complexes of oxovanadium(IV), the present studies were aimed at determining the formation constants of mixed ligand complexes of oxovanadium(IV) with salicylic acid (SA)/5-sulphosalicylic acid (SSA)/8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (HQSA) as primary ligands and hippuric acid as secondary ligand in aqueous medium.

Experimental

Reagents :

Vanadyl solution : A standard solution of vanadyl sulphate (BDH) was prepared as described earlier³.

Ligand solutions : Salicylic acid (AnalaR BDH) and hippuric acid (AnalaR BDH) solutions were prepared by direct weighing in doubly distilled water and their strengths were checked potentiometrically. 5-Sulphosalicylic acid (AnalaR Riedel) was dissolved as monopotassium salt. 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (Kodak) was recrystallized first from water and weighed out directly for each investigation on account of its low solubility.

Ionic strength : The ionic strength of all the reaction mixtures was kept approximately constant ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) using requisite amount of potassium nitrate solution.

Instrument and method : A battery operated bench pattern type Cambridge pH-meter which was calibrated before use with potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax

buffers, was used for all the pH-measurements and the temperature of the reaction mixtures was maintained at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ using a thermostat. The pH-titrations of the following solutions (total volume 50 ml) in aqueous medium were carried out against 0.1 M potassium hydroxide solution free from carbon dioxide:

- (i) 10.00 ml (0.025M) SA/ SSA/ HQSA/ Hippuric acid.
- (ii) 10.00 ml (0.025M) SA/ SSA/ HQSA/ Hippuric acid + 10.00 ml (0.025M) vanadyl sulphate (1 : 1).
- (iii) 10.00 ml (0.025M) SA/ SSA/ HQSA + 10.00 ml (0.025M) Hippuric acid + 10.00 ml (0.025M) vanadyl sulphate (1 : 1 : 1).

Results and Discussion

The pH-titration curves of SA, SSA, HQSA, hippuric acid and vanadyl sulphate in presence of an equimolar concentration of these ligands have been described earlier^{3,4}, and the calculation of the acid dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of primary ligands and pK'_1 of secondary ligand; equilibrium (K_1) and stability (K_{MA}) constants of 1:1 chelates and hydrolysis constants of monohydroxo derivatives of 1:1 chelates have also been reported (Table 1).

Curves 9-11 (Fig. 1) represent the pH-titration of vanadyl sulphate in presence of equimolar amount of one of the primary ligands ($H_2A = SA/ SSA/ HQSA$) and hippuric acid (HL) as secondary ligand. The curve for ternary system, $VO^{2+} - HQSA -$ hippuric acid (Curve 11, Fig. 1) superimpose over the corresponding 1:1 $VO^{2+} - HQSA$ titration curve (Curve 7, Fig. 1) in the initial stage and the lowering of the curve, which is a measure of the mixed ligand chelate formation

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TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND EQUILIBRIUM, FORMATION AND HYDROLYSIS CONSTANTS OF 1:1 CHELATES ($t = 30 \pm 0.5^\circ$; $\mu = 0.1M$ KNO_3)

Ligand	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1'	$-\log K_1$	$\log K_{MA}$	$-\log K_H$
SA	2.99	13.60	—	3.41	13.18	8.04
SSA	2.68	11.42	—	2.73	11.37	7.07
HQSA	4.06	8.49	—	2.07	10.48	5.79
Hippuric acid	—	—	3.61	—	—	4.47

occurs after $m-1$ (m represents the moles of base added per mole of the metal ion or ligand). For other ternary systems, VO^{2+} -SA/SSA-hippuric acid, the curves (9 and 10, Fig. 1) run slightly below the titration curves for 1:1 VO^{2+} -SA/SSA systems from the very beginning. However, all the curves for ternary systems run much below the curve (Curve 8, Fig. 1) for 1:1 VO^{2+} -hippuric acid system. The lowering of the curves for ternary systems inferred the formation of a new species which may be a 1:1:1 ternary complex. Further, it also indicates that ternary complex formation occurs through the formation of 1:1 complexes with primary ligands. The formation of ternary complexes is also supported by the analysis of the potentiometric data.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of mixed ligand chelates; $VO(IV)$ -SA/SSA/HQSA-hippuric acid: 1, SA; 2, SSA; 3, HQSA; 4, hippuric acid; 5,6,7 & 8 $VO(IV)$ -SA/SSA/HQSA/Hippuric acid (1:1); 9,10 & 11, $VO(IV)$ -SA/SSA/HQSA-Hippuric acid (1:1:1).

Assuming the absence of the species $VOAL_2^{2+}$, VOA_2L^{2-} etc when the ratio of metal ion to ligands is

1:1:1 and the formation of only mono nuclear metal chelate species, the equilibria involved in the formation of 1:1:1 mixed ligand complexes in the above systems, may be represented as:

and overall reaction for the formation of the mixed ligand chelate as:

In the pH -range studied (upto $pH \sim 4$) neglecting the concentration of OH^- , A^{2-} and hydrolysed species of vanadyl ions in comparison with those of other species present in the equilibrium mixture, the following equations are obtained for maintaining the material balance:

$$T_M = [VO^{2+}] + [VOA] + [VOAL^-] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$T_A = [H_2A] + [HA^-] + [VOA] + [VOAL^-] \quad \dots (2)$$

$$T_L = [HL] + [L^-] + [VOAL^-] \quad \dots (3)$$

$$T_{OH} + [H^+] = [HA^-] + [L^-] + 2[VOA] + 3[VOAL^-] \quad \dots (4)$$

where T_M , T_A and T_L represent the total concentrations of metal, primary and secondary ligand species respectively and T_{OH} is the concentration of the base added to the reaction mixture during the titration. The hydrolysis of 1:1 VO^{2+} -SA/SSA/HQSA chelate, VOA was also considered to be negligible in the presence of secondary ligand.

In a 1:1 reaction mixture, using the equations (1)-(4) and the relations for the dissociation constants of ligands and equilibrium constant (K_1) of the reaction:

$$a [VO^{2+}] + b [VO^{2-}] - c = 0 \quad \dots (5)$$

where, $a = K_1/[H^+]^2$, $b = xy + x + y$, $c = \{(3-m) T_M - [H^+]\}xy$, $x = 1 + k_1/[H^+]$, $y = 1 + k_1'/[H^+]$ and $[H^+] = \text{antilog}(O - pH)$.

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM AND CHELATE FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES

System	$-\log K'$	$-\log K''$	$\log K_{MAL}$	$\log \beta_{MAL}$
VO^{2+} —SA—hippuric acid	2.01 ± 0.07	5.42 ± 0.07	1.60 ± 0.07	14.78 ± 0.07
VO^{2+} —SSA—hippuric acid	1.44 ± 0.08	4.17 ± 0.08	2.17 ± 0.08	13.54 ± 0.08
VO^{2+} —HQSA—hippuric acid	1.54 ± 0.11	3.61 ± 0.11	2.07 ± 0.11	12.55 ± 0.11

k_1 is the first dissociation constant of the primary ligand and k_1' that of the secondary ligand. The concentration of free vanadyl ions present in the solution at various points of the titration curves for the ternary systems was calculated by solving equation (5). The concentration of other species involved in the equilibrium relations were calculated and also the equilibrium constants K' and K'' of the reactions (i) and (ii) respectively at different points of the titration curves.

Formation constants of 1:1:1 mixed ligand chelates: After determining the equilibrium constants of the reactions for the formation of mixed ligand chelates, the values of formation constant (K_{MAL}) and overall formation constant (β_{MAL}) for the 1:1:1 mixed ligand chelate was calculated using the following relations:

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{[VOAL^-]}{[VOA][L^-]} = \frac{K'}{k_1'} \quad \dots (6)$$

and

$$\beta_{MAL} = \frac{[VOAL^-]}{[VO^{2+}][HA^-][L^-]} = \frac{K''}{k_1 k_2 k_1'} \quad \dots (7)$$

Constant values of the equilibrium and formation constants have been obtained only upto $m=2.2$ and 2.6 in the case of VO^{2+} —SA/SSA—hippuric acid and VO^{2+} —HQSA—hippuric acid systems respectively and beyond that a gradual increase in the values of the formation constants is observed. The gradual increase in the values inferred the formation of hydroxo derivatives of 1:1:1 mixed ligand chelates and their

formation begins before the complete formation of the ternary complexes. This is also indicated by the titration curves for the ternary systems since there is no inflection at $m=3$ and only one inflection after $m=4$ is observed in all these cases. The results are presented in Table 2.

The order of stability of the ternary complexes has been found to be the same as that of 1:1 binary complexes of oxovanadium(IV) with hydroxy acids and can be explained on the basis of the presence of sulphonate group is SSA and HQSA and the steric factors as described earlier⁹.

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